

Coloured Chelates of Pyrogallol Red with Trivalent Aluminium, Gallium and Indium

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4:5:6-trihydroxy-3-oxo-9-(phenyl-o-sulphonic acid) xanthenes (Pyrogallol red; PGR) reacts with trivalent aluminium, gallium and indium to yield violet coloured chelates. The wavelength maxima of the aluminium chelate is 520 m μ and that of gallium and indium chelates is at 530 m μ . The metal: ligand ratio in all the cases is 1:1. The average values of log K (K =stability constant) at 25° as calculated by three different methods using absorbance data is 5.0 for aluminium chelate at pH 4.5, 4.9 for gallium chelate at pH 4.5 and 4.8 for indium chelate at pH 4.5. The coloured complexes conform to Beer's law over the aluminium concentration of 0.11 to 1.9 ppm, gallium concentration of 0.28-5.04 ppm and indium concentration of 0.46-8.28 ppm.

4:5:6-trihydroxy-3-oxo-9-(phenyl-o-sulphonic acid) xanthenes, (trivial name Pyrogallol red; abbr: PGR) has the following structure:

Pyrogallol red.

The literature of metal chelates of PGR is scanty. Vodak and Leminger¹¹ for the first time in 1956 described its use as a colorimetric reagent for silver. Dagnall and West³ and West¹³ reported the optimum conditions under which this reagent may be employed for the detection and determination of silver. The interference of practically every ion except Cu(II) can be eliminated by the addition of controlled amounts of EDTA as a masking agent. Tanaka, Nakagawa and Hona¹⁰ noted the reaction of aluminium, Staroscik and Landgorski⁹ studied the colour reactions of indium with PGR but they did not describe the

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chelate in sufficient detail. This paper records the details of its composition and stability. Also the formation of a pink violet chelate between gallium—FGR has been noted for the first time. Thallium does not produce any colour at all with PGR.

EXPERIMENTAL

A solution of aluminium sulphate (BDH AnalaR) was prepared in water and the solutions of gallium and indium were prepared by dissolving the corresponding chlorides (Johnson and Matthey) acidulated with hydrochloric acid and were standardised. A standard solution of PGR (E. Merck) was prepared by dissolving a known amount in alcohol. The compound have molecular formula $C_{19}H_{12}O_6S$ and was a brownish red powder. Fresh solutions were prepared every day. Solutions of required concentrations were obtained by suitable dilutions. The solutions of the order of $10^{-4} M$ were employed so that the dye behaved as a true solution, as had been ascertained. Absorbance measurements were carried out with a Unicam SP 500 Spectrometer against distilled water blanks using 10 mm glass cells. Hydrogen-ion concentrations were measured with a Leeds and Northrup direct-reading pH indicator. All experiments were carried out at $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. The total volume of all the mixtures prepared for the measurements was kept at 25 ml. pH was adjusted to 4.5 ± 0.1 by addition of hydrochloric acid or sodium hydroxide in all the three cases. The composition of the chelate was obtained by (i) the method of continuous variations⁶, (ii) the mole ratio method¹⁴ and (iii) the slope ratio method⁵ (using absorbance measurements). The apparent stability constant was calculated from the absorbance data using the modified method of Anderson and coworkers¹⁻⁴ as adopted by (a) Dey and coworkers⁷⁻⁸ and further corroborated by the (b) continuous variations method using non-equimolecular solutions and also by the (c) mole ratio method as suggested by Yoe and Jones¹⁴.

FIG. 1

Determination of the composition by the method of continuous variations using equimolecular solutions at 520 m μ ($p=1$; pH 4.5). Curve A: $c=10.0 \times 10^{-5} M$; Curve B: $c=8.0 \times 10^{-5} M$; Curve C: $c=6.67 \times 10^{-5} M$;

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FIG. 2

Determination of the composition by the method of continuous variations using equimolecular solutions at 530 m μ ($p=1$; pH 4.5).

Curve A: $c=10.0 \times 10^{-5}$ M; Curve B: $c=8.0 \times 10^{-5}$ M;

Curve C: $c=6.67 \times 10^{-5}$ M.;

FIG. 3

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Properties of the reagent and absorption spectra: It has been observed in the case of PGR that the colour develops rapidly in a small volume and is stable on dilution, but if the solution is diluted immediately the colour intensity is low and the colour develops slowly. It has also been observed that the sensitivity in aqueous solution is not high but the colour is stable for more than twenty four hours. On the other hand, if an alcoholic solution is used, it gives a high sensitivity with metal ions but the colour is not stable for more than twelve hours.

It is interesting to examine the variation of colour of PGR with respect to hydrogen ion concentration. The absorbance measurement of 5.0×10^{-5} M PGR solution was made at different pH values. The change of $\lambda_{\max}$ with pH is tabulated below.

TABLE I

Variation of $\lambda_{\max}$ of PGR with pH

pH	max (m μ)
below 3.0	470
3.0-4.0	480
4.0-5.4	510
5.4-6.6	550

Above pH 6.6 the colour of the dye fades rapidly and hence the absorption measurements were not possible above that pH.

Nature of the complex formed: The wavelength of maximum absorption was determined by the method of Vosburgh and Cooper¹². The absorbance values of mixtures in various ratios of the reactants show that only one complex is formed under the conditions of study with λ_{max} 520m μ for aluminium chelate, λ_{max} 530 m μ for gallium chelate and λ_{max} 520 m μ for indium chelate.

Tables II, III and IV summarise the results from the method of continuous variations using absorbance measurements. To economise space the values are given at only one wavelength.

TABLE II

Experiment	Curve	$c \times 10^5$ (M)	p	λ (m μ)	Volume of aluminium (ml) at peak.	Composition of the chelate Al:PGR
1 (Fig.1)	A	10.00	1.0	520	12.5	1:1
	B	8.00	1.0	520	12.5	1:1
	C	6.67	1.0	520	12.5	1:1

TABLE III

Experiment	Curve	$c \times 10^5$ (M)	p	λ (m μ)	Volume of gallium (ml) at peak.	Composition of the chelate Ga: PGR
1 (Fig. 2)	A	10.00	1.0	530	12.5	1:1
	B	8.00	1.0	530	12.5	1:1
	C	6.67	1.0	530	12.5	1:1

TABLE IV

Experiment	Curve	$c \times 10^5$ (M)	p	λ (m μ)	Volume of indium (ml) at peak	Composition of the chelate In: PGR
1 (Fig.3)	A	10.00	1.0	530	12.5	1:1
	B	8.00	1.0	530	12.5	1:1
	C	6.67	1.0	530	12.5	1:1

Results obtained by the other methods mentioned above corroborate the composition of the chelate.

Measurements at different pH values and at various wavelengths indicate that aluminium chelate is stable at pH 4.0-5.0, gallium chelate at pH 3.5—5.5 and indium chelate at pH 4.0-5.0. Values of $\log K$ determined by three different methods are in close agreement (table V).

Suggestions on the structure of chelate: In the metal chelates involving PGR, there are two alternative positions where chelation may occur. The metal ion may be chelated either (i) between two adjacent phenolic oxygens or (ii) between quinoid oxygen and the adjacent phenolic oxygen.

TABLE V

Stability constants of the Chelates.

Metal Chelate	$\log K (25^\circ)$	pH	Method
Al-PGR	4.9 ± 0.1	4.5	(a)
	4.9 ± 0.1		(b)
	5.2 ± 0.1		(c)
Ga-PGR	4.4 ± 0.1	4.5	(a)
	5.0 ± 0.1		(b)
	5.3 ± 0.1		(c)
In-PGR	4.3 ± 0.1	4.5	(a)
	5.0 ± 0.1		(b)
	5.2 ± 0.1		(c)

M stands for Al(III), Ga (III) and In (III)

In the chelates investigated here it was found that when solution of aluminium (III), gallium (III) and indium (III) metals and PGR (both individually adjusted to pH 4.5) were mixed, the pH dropped to 4.1 showing the liberation of hydrogen ions as a result of chelation. Thus it is tentatively suggested that the chelation of the metals takes place between two adjacent phenolic oxygen.

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